

INSTRUCTIONAL INFORMATION

The following module template has been developed as part of Work Package 7 of the EU-funded GoGreen project. The module is designed in a skeletal format to allow for broad adaptation to a wide range of existing curricula and professional development schemes. To enhance flexibility, the module is divided into theme blocks with suggested content, assessments, and activities. The template has been constructed to serve as foundational material for curriculum development or course integration.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

This module may be adapted for the instruction of conservation and conservation science learners at the undergraduate, postgraduate, and professional level with a focus on paintings. The activities and assessments of this module are developed for a group audience.

MODULE DELIVERY

This module is best suited for in-person, practical instruction. Recommended module delivery is through the utilisation of individual case studies, either mock-ups, paintings, or previous work. Throughout the module learners will have the opportunity to:

- Conduct tests on their case study using various solvents and application methods
- Observe and record the effects of the different cleaning materials and methods by employing the Fife Solvent Star
- Utilise analytical techniques and simple assessment approaches to assess, compare, and evaluate the effectiveness of various solvents and application methods and link these with information about their environmental impact.

PRE-REQUISITE KNOWLEDGE

Prior to the module, learners should be prepped with the following skills and knowledge which may be acquired from previous coursework or through complementary GoGreen modules:

1. Knowledge of the foundational principles for paintings conservation and the effects of solvents on paint films.
2. Awareness of policies, frameworks, and methodologies within the cultural heritage sector that may be applied to the remedial conservation of paintings. Supported by the GoGreen module ***Leadership in Green Conservation***
3. Knowledge of the GoGreen definition for green conservation and green parameters, and the Green Decision-Making Model (DMM). Supported by the GoGreen module ***Leadership in Green Conservation***
4. Knowledge of green tools and frameworks that may be applied for the assessment of material sensitivity for informed decision-making in conservation and cultural heritage care. Supported by the GoGreen module ***Determining Material Sensitivities and Green Decision-making***

MISSION STATEMENT

To empower students and professionals to make informed green(er) choices in their personal practice by integrating tools, metrics, and guidelines for selecting and evaluating green(er) cleaning materials and methods for the remedial conservation of paintings.

DESCRIPTION

Green Treatments and Their Assessment: Paintings explores the green frameworks, tools, and guidelines relevant for the selection and application of green(er) materials and methods for the conservation of paintings. The content emphasises the cleaning stage of remedial conservation, focusing on recent advancements in green(er) solvents, solutions, and retention systems developed within the GoGreen project and broader EU-funded Green Cluster. Additionally, it covers the efficacy, safety, and ethical considerations of these materials and methods, and demonstrates how the frameworks and tools may be applied to other remedial conservation practices.

Content is delivered through practical, case study-based learning, supporting student-centred development of both theoretical and practical skills. Learners are encouraged to apply green thinking to their own conservation practice or a selected case study, reflecting on the practicalities, challenges, and limitations of sustainable approaches in real-world contexts.

LEARNING GOALS AND OUTCOMES

Main Goal Provide conservation researchers and conservators with the knowledge and practical tools needed for the development, assessment and use of green(er) approaches for the cleaning of paintings

Subsidiary Goals

- Develop an understanding of the application of tools, metrics, and guidelines to support green(er) decision-making to the conservation of paintings
- Explore new solvents, solutions, and retention systems used for the remedial conservation of paintings, and assess their impact on the environment, human health and well-being, resources, and cultural heritage in comparison to commonly used materials
- Evaluate the efficacy of cleaning materials utilising new assessment techniques from the GoGreen project
- Develop practical knowledge through the application of greener cleaning approaches and reflect on personal practice using the green conservation definition and parameters

By the end of this module,

Learning Outcomes

1. **(Evaluation)** Evaluate the 'greenness' of materials used in the cleaning of paintings by applying the Green Parameters and frameworks: (1) Globally Harmonized System (GHS), (2) Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA), (3) Safe and Sustainable by Design principles, and (4) Guidelines.
2. **(Comparison)** Compare cleaning strategies used in the remedial conservation of paintings, considering their impact through a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.
3. **(Assessment)** Gain knowledge of new analytical techniques and simple assessment approaches to assess treated surfaces to compare and evaluate different applications and materials for the cleaning of paintings.
4. **(Reflection)** Demonstrate theoretical and practical competency in reflecting on the selection and application of green(er) cleaning methods for painting conservation by discussing the processes, decisions, and outcomes involved in their application on a case study.

RECOMMENDED READINGS

Visit the GoGreen Zenodo for the full module bibliography

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- Wang, C., Cao, Y., Tie, F., & Camaiti, M.** (2022). Er:YAG Laser Cleaning of Painted Surfaces: Functional Considerations to Improve Efficacy and Reduce Side Effects. In *Conservation Tools, Protocols and Treatments on Painted Surfaces, Metal Leaves and Finishes in Cultural Heritage* (pp. 43). MDPI - Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute.
- United Nations.** (2023). *Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals* (10th ed.). <https://unece.org/transport/dangerous-goods/ghs-rev10-2023>

SUPPLEMENTARY READINGS

- Zaratti, C., Marinelli, L., Colasanti, I. A., Barbaccia, F. I., Aureli, H., Prestileo, F., De Caro, T., La Russa, M. F., & Macchia, A.** (2024). Evaluation of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME) as a Green Alternative to Common Solvents in Conservation Treatments. *Applied Sciences*, 14(5), 1970. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14051970>
- Husby, L. M., Andersen, C. K., Pedersen, N. B., & Ormsby, B.** (2023). Evaluating three water-based systems and one organic solvent for the removal of dammar varnish from artificially aged oil paint samples. *Heritage Science*, 11(1), 244. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-023-01077-1>
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GREEN TREATMENTS AND THEIR ASSESSMENT: PAINTINGS

THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	ACTIVITIES + ASSESSMENTS
Foundation and Tools for the Green Conservation of Paintings	<i>Green Frameworks and Tools for Sustainable Decision-Making in Painting Conservation</i>	<p>Explores green conservation, the green frameworks, and practical tools for sustainable decision-making in painting conservation.</p>	<p>Evaluate the ‘greenness’ of materials used in the cleaning of paintings by applying the Green Parameters and frameworks: (1) Globally Harmonized System (GHS), (2) Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA), (3) Safe and Sustainable by Design principles, and (4) Guidelines.</p>	<p>Group Activity: Read the Green(er) Steps in Chapter 3: Practical Steps to <i>Green(er) Solutions by Gwendoline Fife in Green(er) Solvents in Conservation: An Introductory Guide</i> and complete Step 1: Studio Solvent Cupboard Assessment utilise relevant green frameworks and tools to complete activity.</p> <p>Individual Assessment: Using relevant green frameworks and tools, evaluate the ‘greenness’ of a conservation material commonly used within personal context and present findings.</p> <p>Activity: Choose and use a tool for green(er) decision-making on a provided case study for the remedial conservation of paintings. Consider the appropriateness of the treatment using a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.</p>
Introduction to Solvents and Solutions	<i>Cleaning Agents for Paintings: Solvents and Solutions</i>	<p>Explores green(er) advancements in solvents and solutions for cleaning paintings, and how they compare to traditional approaches.</p> <p>Solvents and solutions developed within the Green Cluster are highlighted in more detail to provide a foundation for practical application.</p>	<p>Compare cleaning strategies used in the remedial conservation of paintings, considering their impact through a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.</p>	<p>Activity: Investigate 2 to 3 newly identified green(er) solvents and solutions. Create a properties profile that include the physical properties, toxicity and hazard metrics, and LCA impact of chosen solvents or solutions.</p>
	<i>Practical Application of Cleaning Agents</i>	<p>Practical session focused on the application of cleaning agents highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going innovations. Utilising suggested module delivery for instruction.</p>		<p>Activity: Apply solvents and solutions identified in the previous activity, alongside commonly used solvents (including petroleum based), to a case study to expand the properties profile to include practical assessments. Exchange with fellow students and identify how they compare against commonly used approaches utilising the green frameworks. Consider effective communication strategies for presenting the full profile to broader class, for example, include star diagrams, solvent stars, etc.</p>
Introduction to Retention Systems	<i>Retention Systems for the Cleaning of Paintings</i>	<p>Introduces new retention systems for cleaning, highlighting materials and techniques developed in the Green Cluster projects and ongoing innovations. Green conservation parameters are applied to compare and contrast retention and free solvent systems, supporting sustainable decision-making in conservation practice.</p>	<p>Compare cleaning strategies used in the remedial conservation of paintings, considering their impact through a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.</p>	<p>Activity: Investigate 2 to 3 newly identified retention systems and create a profile based on the safe and sustainable by design framework.</p>
	<i>Practical Application of Retention Systems</i>	<p>Practical session focused on the application of retention systems highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going innovations. Utilising suggested module delivery for instruction.</p>		<p>Activity: Apply retention systems outlined in the previous activity on a case study to expand the properties profile to include practical assessments. Exchange with fellow students and identify how they compare against commonly used approaches utilising the green frameworks. Consider effective communication strategies for presenting the full profile to broader class, for example, include star diagrams, solvent stars, etc.</p>

GREEN TREATMENTS AND THEIR ASSESSMENT: PAINTINGS

THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	ACTIVITIES + ASSESSMENTS
Testing and Monitoring of Treated Surfaces	<i>Introduction to Assessment Techniques for the Evaluation of Cleaning Strategies</i>	Introduces new analytical techniques and simple assessment methods developed for the evaluation of cleaning efficacy in the remedial conservation of paintings. Taking into consideration risks, benefits, and limitations.	Gain knowledge of new analytical techniques and simple assessment approaches to assess treated surfaces to compare and evaluate different applications and materials for the cleaning of paintings.	Activity/Assessment: Present on a specific key risk, benefit, or limitation of 1-2 analytical techniques or simple assessment methods.
	<i>Practical: Application of Assessment Techniques</i>	Practical session focused on the application of assessment techniques highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going research. Utilising suggested module delivery for instruction.		<p>Activity: Explore when and how new analytical techniques can be applied using green parameters and assess their added value in treatment or research. Reflect on how these techniques and methods can become part of your own conservation toolbox.</p> <p>Activity: Apply available monitoring and cleaning assessment techniques the case study to evaluate the efficacy of cleaning materials and application methods. Expand the properties profile created in earlier activities to include the efficacy of the materials and application methods.</p> <p>Assessment: Present full properties profile using visual communications strategies.</p>
Conservation Practice	<i>Putting into Practice</i>	Provides learners with the opportunity to apply new knowledge to personal context by integrating green(er) thinking into existing conservation practice or on a case study and assessing the practicalities and limitations.	Demonstrate theoretical and practical competency in reflecting on the selection and application of green(er) cleaning methods for painting conservation by discussing the processes, decisions, and outcomes involved in their application on a case study.	<p>Activity/Assessment: Present on a case study identifying strategies for integrating green(er) strategies in one's professional practice. Analyse the practicality and limitations of suggested strategies in real world contexts.</p> <p>Activity/Assessment: Create a mood board for a personal mission statement.</p> <p>Activity: Group discussion How can different stakeholders contribute to greener decision-making within the complexities of cultural heritage conservation?</p>

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

AUTHORS AND CONTRIBUTORS

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